

Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), and adaptive trials and in crop cutting experiments in farmers' fields.

Yield increase was 14-40% compared with IR20 and 13-15% compared with Jaya (see table). In AICRIP trials, it was superior to Jaya at six locations during the wet season and two locations during the dry season.

ADT39 is resistant to bacterial blight, blast, neck blast, brown spot, sheath blight, and grain discoloration;

moderately resistant to green leafhopper; and susceptible to sheath rot, leafhopper, and brown planthopper. (However, BPH is not a problem in the season in which it is grown.)

ADT39 has 65% milling recovery and 10.1% protein. The fine-grained rice cooks well and is highly preferred in South India. Farmers of Tamil Nadu have named it "Idly rice" and "tiffin rice." The Agricultural Department

estimated its natural spread, before release, in 40,000 ha in Thanjavur district.

ADT39 is already proven well suited to late planting (Oct-Nov) in Thanjavur district. Because it matures earlier than IR20, it should escape water scarcity during ripening, opening room for timely sowing of black gram, green gram, and cotton in the rice fallow season. □

VL Dhan 163 - a new upland rice variety for Uttar Pradesh hills

R. K. Sharma, K. D. Koranne, V. S. Chauhan, D. K. Garg, and J. C. Bhatt, Vivekananda Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala (ICAR), Almora 263601, Uttar Pradesh (U.P.), India

VL Dhan 163, a derivative of IR5904, was released in 1987 for upland Jun sowing in the U.P. hills.

VL Dhan 163 possesses such desirable characteristics as semitall stature, medium grain, and compact panicle with good spikelet fertility. It has moderate tillering ability and matures in 108-113 d. It is tolerant of drought and

low temperature and shows good response up to 60 kg N/ha. It also has shown high resistance to leaf and neck blast, stem borer, and leafhopper (see table).

In 12 trials at different sites in the U.P. hills, VL Dhan 163 produced an average 2.6 t/ha, 41.35% higher than the

national check Bala.

Traditionally, the hill farmers of U.P. grow Mar- or Apr-sown spring rice under rainfed upland conditions in a 2-yr cropping system of spring rice - wheat - finger millet - fallow. With VL Dhan 163, hill farmers will be able to plant two rice crops in a year. □

Plant characteristics of VL Dhan 163 and Bala. Almora, U. P., India, 1987.

Character	VL Dhan 163	Bala (check)
Plant height (cm)	95-100	65-70
Days to 50% flowering	75-80	80-85
Days to maturity	108-113	105-110
1000-grain weight (g)	19.0	16.0
Hulling percentage	85.4	83.7
Grain length (mm)	5.4	4.6
Grain width (mm)	2.2	2.4
Length/width ratio	2.4	1.9
Protein content	9.3	9.0
Yield (t/ha)	2.6	1.8
<i>Disease & insect pest reaction^a</i>		
Leaf blast (0-9 scale)	3	9
Neck blast (0-9 scale)	1	9
Sheath rot (0-9 scale)	3	7
False smut (0-9 scale)	1	5
Stem borer (0-9 scale)	3	5
Leafhopper (0-9 scale)	1	5

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice. Maximum score recorded during any year 1983-86.

Performance of semidwarf mutants of Basmati 370

A. A. Cheema and M. A. Awan, Nuclear Institute for Agriculture and Biology, P. O. Box 128, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan

Four semidwarf mutants (gamma

radiation 25 kR) were selected from the segregating population and yield tested in the field. The short-statured mutants gave significantly higher grain yields than parent variety Basmati 370 and had high tillering ability (Table 1) and lodging resistance. Growth duration was similar to Basmati 370. The semidwarf

Table 1. Performance of the induced mutant lines and Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan.

Mutant, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Duration (d)	Productive tillers (ns./plant)	Yield (g/plant)	Yield (t/ha)
DM24	122.7	105	15	25	4.6
DM25	125.7	106	15	24	4.6
DM28	131.3	105	12	22	4.2
DM38	121.7	105	14	23	4.1
Basmati 370	160.5	104	12	21	4.0
LSD (0.05)	4.2	ns	2	1	0.1

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of rice mutants and Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan.

Variety, mutant	Length ^a (mm)	Width ^a (mm)	Length-to-width ratio ^a	Quality index ^a	Elongation ratio ^a	Amylose ^b (%)
DM24	6.9	1.8	3.9	2.3	1.9	24
DM25	6.7	1.7	3.9	2.4	1.9	23
DM28	6.6	1.7	3.8	2.5	1.7	23
DM38	6.7	1.7	3.8	2.4	1.8	23
Basmati 370	6.9	1.8	3.8	2.3	1.8	23
LSD (0.05)	0.15	ns	ns	0.10	ns	ns

^aAv of 10 determinations. ^bAv of 3 determinations.